

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Calcined Eggshell: An Environmentally Benign Green Catalyst For Synthesis Of Newer Acetamide Derivatives And Its Antimicrobial Activity

Jayshree Kokat^{1*}, Bharat Jadhav², Rajesh Mokate³, Puja Aher⁴

¹Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Abasaheb Kakade College of Pharmacy, Bodhegaon 414503 Ahmednagar Maharashtra

²Department of Pharmaceutics, Abasaheb Kakade College of B Pharmacy, Bodhegaon 414503 Ahmednagar Maharashtra

³Department of Pharmacognosy, Abasaheb Kakade College of Pharmacy, Bodhegaon 414503 Ahmednagar Maharashtra

⁴Department of Pharmacognosy, Abasaheb Kakade College of Pharmacy, Bodhegaon 414503 Ahmednagar Maharashtra

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 30 Aug 2024

Accepted: 04 Aug 2024

Published: 23 Aug 2024

Keywords:

Acetamide, Antimicrobial, Coumarin, Thiazole, Minimum inhibitory concentration, zone of inhibition.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13367362

ABSTRACT

For the synthesis of a series of novel Coumarin derivatives, an efficient and easy approach has been designed. ¹H-NMR and Fourier Transformed infrared (FTIR) are used to characterise the structures of freshly synthesised compounds, which are then evaluated for antibacterial activity in vitro by calculating zone of inhibition and minimum inhibitory concentration. The antibacterial and antifungal activity of 4-[(2-oxo-2-[5-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-3-yl)-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]aminoethyl]amino]benzoic acid was comparable to that of ciprofloxacin and fluconazole. The remaining compounds had moderate to good activity.

INTRODUCTION

The growing issue of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has made the development of novel

antimicrobial drugs a top goal in modern medicine.

This talk explores the methods, obstacles, and developments in the creation of new antimicrobial

***Corresponding Author:** Jayshree Kokat

Address: Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Abasaheb Kakade College of Pharmacy, Bodhegaon 414503 Ahmednagar Maharashtra

Email ✉: jayshreekokat4@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

medications, highlighting the necessity of a multimodal strategy that incorporates cutting-edge research methods and interdisciplinary cooperation. Solvents, which are required for the synthesis of new drugs and are either toxic or flammable, significantly increase the overall cost of synthesis. Green chemistry (catalyst) often improves selectivity, speeds up reactions, and makes product separation and purification simpler than traditional methods. Among the few parts of green science, the decrease or substitution of unstable natural solvents from the response medium is of most extreme significance. Chemists must now look for as many environmentally friendly methods as possible due to the growing economic and environmental concerns in recent years. In ongoing work we utilize the green methodology by utilizing less risky impetus calcinated egg shell (CES) for the combination of new acetamide derivates [1]. Antibiotics have saved countless lives through research and commercialization, making them one of the most commonly prescribed antibiotics today. Several bacterial diseases, including diarrhea, food poisoning, and rheumatic fever, are brought on by multidrug-resistant bacteria. Resistance to antibiotics that are currently available is rapidly rising, posing a serious threat to human health². One of the most active classes of chemicals, coumarin and its derivatives has a wide range of biological effects. Antibacterial, antifungal, calming, anticoagulant, against HIV, and anticancer properties have been exhibited for a few of these substances. Various subbed coumarin analogs have antibacterial, anticonvulsant, acetyl cholinesterase inhibitory, and aldehyde correct inhibitory properties.[3, 4, 5] A crucial area of research for the growing interest in thiazole chemistry is the design of novel compounds and the wide variety of pharmaceutical and medical applications for which they can be used. Many natural bioactive substances, like marine alkaloids,

have the thiazole ring as a fundamental structural component. The thiazole ring (antineoplastic drug) is present in penicillin (wide-spectrum antibiotic), sulfathiazole (antimicrobial drug), ritonavir (antiretroviral drug), abafungin (antifungal drug), and tiazofurin (antifungal drug).[6, 7, 9, 10]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Merck, Germany, and Loba Organization provided all synthetic substances and solvents. ¹HNMR spectra were obtained using Bruker Advance 500 MHZ equipment. Utilizing thin-layer chromatography (TLC), the purity of the was determined. Using an electronic Veego (model:-VMP-D), the melting points were determined in an open capillary. The synthesized compounds' IR spectra were obtained using the Shimadzu 8400 FT-IR Spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of 3-acetyl-2H-chromen-2-one

The solution was made up of 25.65mL (0.1mol) ethyl acetoacetate and 21.29mL (0.1mol) salicylaldehyde. In an ice bath, it was chilled. Rapid stirring was used to add 2ml (0.02mol) of piperidine to the liquid. The reaction mixture was held at a low temperature. The yellowish material was separated after 20 minutes, filtered, and washed with ethanol thereafter. It was recrystallized from ethanol from ethanol: water (7:3)[10]. Yield-85%, Melting point-110-114°C, IR Spectra (KBr) - C=O (α , β unsaturated) at 1600 to 1700 cm^{-1} in addition to ketone C=O at 1745 to 1715 cm^{-1} , aliphatic C-H 3000 to 2850 cm^{-1} , aromatic C-H 3150 to 3000 cm^{-1} .

Synthesis of 2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carbonyl bromide

4.7gm (0.025mol) 3-acetylcoumarin was taken in a beaker and dissolved in 20 ml of chloroform. 4gm (0.05mol) bromine was taken in round bottom flask. 13 ml of chloroform was added to it. The two mixtures were mixed by slowly stirring and refluxed for 1hr. After 1hr reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and washed with petroleum ether. It was recrystallized from ethanol: chloroform

(2:1)[5]. Yield-78%, Melting point-140-1440c, IR Spectra- C-Br at 756 cm⁻¹, lactone at 1700 to 1600 cm⁻¹, ketone C=O at 1745 to 1715 cm⁻¹, aromatic C=C at 2350 to 2100 cm⁻¹, aromatic C-H 3150 to 3000 cm⁻¹.

Synthesis of 3-(5-amino-1, 3-thiazol-2-yl)-2H-chromen-2-one

1gm of 3-bromo acetyl coumarin (1mol) and 1gm (1mol) of thiourea were taken in 250 ml of round bottom flask and dissolved in 20 ml of ethanol by slowly stirring for 15min. After 15 min 0.5ml of ammonia was added to it. The reaction mixture was heated under the reflux for 30min. After 30min the reaction mixture was poured in ice cold water (50ml), filtered and dried. It was recrystallized from ethanol [11]. Yield-85%, Melting point-220-2220c, IR Spectra(KBr) - C-S at 635 to 500 cm⁻¹, aromatic C=N at 1660 to 1340 cm⁻¹, lactone at 1700 to 1600 cm⁻¹, amine N-H at 3500 to 3100 -1cm.

Synthesis of 2-chloro-N-[2-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-3yl)-1, 3-thiazol-5-] acetamide

In round bottom flask, 0.7gm (0.005mole) of 3-(5-amino-1, 3-thiazol-2-yl)-2H-chromen-2-one, 0.5gm of anhydrous potassium carbonate and 1ml of triethyl amine were taken and dissolved into 65ml of dry chloroform with slowly stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4-5hr. After 5hr the reaction mixture was evaporated. The resulting

solid was washed with cold water and dried. It was recrystallized from ethanol: water (80:20)[12]. Yield-85%, Melting point-230-2320c, IR Spectra (KBr) 591 (C-S), 643 (C-Cl), 1249 (C-O), 1319 (C-N), 1556(C=N), 1651(C=O), 1735(keto C=O), 1797(amide N-H), 2327(Ar C=C), 3078(C-H), 3140(Ar C-H), 3371(amine N-H)

Synthesis of 1-(substituted phenyl)-3-[4-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-3-yl)-1, 3-thiazol-2-yl]acetamide

3gm (0.13mol) of 2-chloro-N-[2-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-3yl)-1, 3-thiazol-5-] acetamide and substituted aniline were taken into the mortar. And calcinated egg shell to it which was first calcinated by heating in muffle furnace at very high temperature. This reaction mixture was mix continues with pestle at room temperature for 2hr. After 2 hr the reaction mixture was kept for the TLC solid was separated, which was filtered and dried. It was recrystallized by using ethanol: water (80:20) [3].

RESULTS

Antimicrobial screening of the synthesized compounds for zone of inhibition and Minimum Inhibitory Concentration was performed using the Cup plate method. The Antibacterial action was tried against different gram positive and Gram-negative microorganisms and hostile to parasitic action against different contagious strains contrasted and standard medication.

Table 1: Zone of inhibition of target compounds (5a-5g) for bacteria and fungi

Sr. No	Compound	Conc. µg/ml	Zone of inhibition (mm)			
			S. aureus	B. subtilis	E. coli	P.aeruginosa
1	5a	50	9±1.73	12±1.68TG	7±1.25	10±1.63
		100	10±1.45	14±1.37	9±1.62	12±1.65
		150	12±1.36	15±1.15	11±1.55	15±1.18
2	5b	50	10±1.32	14±1.18	11±1.18	14±1.34
		100	12±1.67	16±1.17	15±1.27	15±1.16
		150	18±1.06	22±1.19	18±1.51	20±1.45
3	5c	50	8±1.34	12±1.34	10±1.10	12±1.38
		100	12±1.65	14±1.36	12±1.73	13±1.34
		150	14±1.46	15±1.65	14±1.52	15±1.16
4	5d	50	6±1.43	8±1.35	8±1.18	11±1.45
		100	7±1.82	10±1.36	10±1.74	13±1.28
		150	9±1.67	12±1.67	12±1.50	15±1.48

5	5e	50	8±1.43	11±1.48	5±1.45	9±1.84
		100	9±1.32	13±1.17	6±1.34	10±1.67
		150	10±1.10	14±1.04	7±1.72	12±1.47
6	5f	50	7±1.16	11±1.36	6±1.78	9±1.67
		100	10±1.25	13±1.58	18±1.23	12±1.43
		150	12±1.06	14±1.14	10±1.18	13±1.17
7	5g	50	8±1.36	8±1.17	8±1.67	11±1.12
		100	10±1.25	9±1.34	10±1.56	12±1.45
		150	12±1.16	12±1.17	12±1.15	12±1.48
Standard	Azithromycin	150	26±1.36	29±1.54	24±1.35	28±1.33

Table 2: Zone of inhibition of compounds target compounds (5a-5g) against fungus species

Sr. No	Compound	Conc. µg/ml	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
			A.niger	C. albicans
1	5a	50	9±1.18	10±1.36
		100	10±1.28	11±1.45
		150	12±1.15	15±1.18
2	5b	50	11±1.36	11±1.17
		100	13±1.39	12±1.23
		150	15±1.11	14±1.18
3	5c	50	14±1.48	10±1.23
		100	15±1.46	12±1.34
		150	17±1.12	14±1.15
4	5d	50	9±1.38	12±1.54
		100	10±1.38	14±1.53
		150	12±1.10	17±1.18
5	5e	50	10±1.30	10±1.36
		100	12±1.63	12±1.52
		150	14±1.72	14±1.17
6	5f	50	11±1.73	12±1.19
		100	12±1.45	13±1.53
		150	14±1.08	14±1.28
7	5g	50	10±1.11	9±1.23
		100	11±1.37	10±1.73
		150	13±1.15	12±1.16
Standard	Fluconazole	150	25±1.35	27±1.33

Table 3: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

Sr. No.	Compound code	S. aureus	B. subtilis	E. coli	P. aeruginosa	A. Niger	C. albicans
1	5a	20	30	40	30	30	40
2	5b	20	20	30	20	30	20
3	5c	40	30	30	40	40	30
4	5d	20	30	30	30	30	40
5	5e	30	20	30	40	30	30
6	5f	40	50	40	40	40	50
7	5g	30	30	30	30	30	40

At a MIC of 20 g/ml, the compound 5b was effective against S. aureus and B. subtilis, respectively. At a MIC of 20 g/ml, the compound

5a was effective against P. aeruginosa and E. coli, respectively. At MICs of 30 and 20 g/ml, respectively, the compound 5b exhibited strong

antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *C. albicans*. Compound 5b has been shown to be effective against Azithromycin at various concentrations, which was the result of research into the antibacterial and antifungal properties of a number of new acetamide derivatives against Stevdord medications. The remaining derivatives' actions were moderate. Against Fluconazole, compounds 5a and 5b have demonstrated strong antifungal properties. The obtained derivatives and the current scheme are novel. Only a few substances have demonstrated promising antibacterial and antifungal properties. However, the best outcomes may be anticipated with the appropriate molecule modification of the derivatives' scheme.

DISCUSSION

The environmentally friendly catalysts we employed in this work, called "green" catalysts (calcinated egg shell), are essential to the advancement of sustainable chemistry. These catalysts are made to promote efficiency, selectivity, and waste reduction by facilitating chemical processes with the least possible negative influence on the environment. These are the main drivers for our efforts to produce novel drugs, which have a number of benefits over existing antimicrobial drugs that are synthesized using more traditional techniques.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, the antibacterial and antifungal activities of new acetamide derivatives are synthesized and biologically assessed. According to the results of an in vitro antimicrobial screening, compounds 5b, 5c, 5d, and 5f all showed moderate activity. Compounds 5e and 5g demonstrated the least efficaciousness against bacteria and fungus. Compound 5a antibacterial and antifungal qualities were on par with the benchmark. As such, we conclude that the coordinated blends possess an additional platform that can serve as a model for the development of new antimicrobial experts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to adv. V. K. Secretary and Sau. H. K., member of ZP and president NMSM Shevgaon for their encouragement. The authors also express sincere thanks to Mr. Rajesh Mokate, Principal Abasaheb Kakade College of Pharmacy Bodhegaon, for their help in making this research.

REFERENCES

1. Patil S, Jadhav S D, Shinde SK. CES as an Efficient Natural Catalyst for Synthesis of Schiff Bases under Solvent-Free Conditions: An Innovative Green Approach. *Organic Chemistry International* 2012, 53159, 5.
2. Zaman SB, Hussain MA, Nye R, Mehta V, Mamun KT and Hossain N. A Review on Antibiotic Resistance. *Alarm Bells are Ringing. Cureus.* 2017; 28;9(6):1403.
3. Ali I, Laila R, Mishbah UR, Rukhsana A, Sami U, Mahwish M, Saba Q . Sadia S. Coumarin sulfonamide derivatives: An emerging class of therapeutic agents. *Heterocyclic Communications* 2020; 26:46-59.
4. Hua LQ, Zai WZ, Lekkala R. Rakesh KP. Antibacterial activities with the structure-activity relationship of coumarin derivatives. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 2020; 207:112832.
5. Fatih S, Belma G, Isil G. Design, synthesis and docking study of novel coumarin ligands as potential selective acetylcholinesterase inhibitors. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry* 2017; 32: 285-297.
6. LAliya I, Yildiz T, Imtiaz K, Abdul H, Aamer S, Norbert F, Jürgen B. Jamshed I. Coumarin-thiazole and oxadiazole derivatives: Synthesis, bioactivity and docking studies for aldose/aldehyde reductase inhibitors. *Bioorganic Chemistry* 2016; 68:177-186.
7. Alshibl HM, Al-Abdullah ES, Haiba ME, Alkahtani HM, Awad GEA, Mahmoud AH, Ibrahim BM, Bari A. Villinger A. Synthesis and Evaluation of New Coumarin Derivatives as Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, and Anti-

- Inflammatory Agents. *Molecules* 2020; 16; 25(14):3251.
8. Ayati A, Emami S, Asadipour A, Shafiee A. Foroumadi A: Recent applications of 1,3-thiazole core structure in the identification of new lead compounds and drug discovery. *Eur J Med Chem* 2015; 5; 97:699-718.
 9. Chhabria MT, Patel S, Modi P. Brahmkshatriya PS. Thiazole: A Review on Chemistry, Synthesis and Therapeutic Importance of its Derivatives. *Curr Top Med Chem* 2016;16(26):2841-2862.
 10. Olayinka OA, Maria MA, Natasha O, Tolutope OS, Damilola VA, Anuoluwa AA . Shade J.O: Microwave assisted synthesis, characterization and investigation of antibacterial activity of 3-(5-(substituted-phenyl)-4, 5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)-2H-chromen-2-one derivatives. *Arab Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*2019; 26:361–374.
 11. Ammar A, Razzak MK, Nedaa A, Hameed A. Rahim. Synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of new-[2-amino-4-(4-chloro-/4-bromophenyl)-1,3-thiazole derivatives. *Journal of Pharmacy Research* 2018;12:145-150.
 12. Shukla MB, Mahayavanshi JB. Joshi PJ. Synthesis and anti-microbial screening of N-(3-cyano-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-1-benzothiophen-2-(aryl phenyl) acetamide. *Indian Journal of Chemistry* 2018; 57B:1222-1227.

HOW TO CITE: Jayshree Kokat , Bharat Jadhav , Rajesh Mokate , Puja Aher , Calcinized Eggshell: An Environmentally Benign Green Catalyst For Synthesis Of Newer Acetamide Derivatives And Its Antimicrobial Activity , *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 8, 3660-3665. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13367362>

